

THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM AND THE THEORY OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN IT.

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Annotation: This article considers the credit-module system, which is currently considered a new system in higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and its history of origin. The main purpose of using this program is to ensure transparency and openness in higher education.

Key words: credit module, mobility, transparency, ECTS, Bologna declaration, Charles Elliot

It is well-known that in our country, there is a special emphasis on such issues as devotion to higher education, its transparency, and the improvement of the system associated with the organization of the teaching process. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev affirmed the concept of developing the higher education system by 2030 and the Action Strategy for the five pillars of National Development during 2017-2021 "Development of Science, Education and the Digital Economy" On March 2, 2020, the PF Decrees No. 5953 set a number of tasks. One such priority and most important task was to gradually switch the educational process in higher education institutions to the credit module system.

The credit module system is an innovation for higher education, a new phase of education. The reason for this is that higher education was surrounded by paperwork left over from the Soviet era and some subjects that have lost their level of importance today and do not accept marketing at all today. The credit system in higher education, on the other hand, is aimed at improving the quality of education, and making the courses and courses more transparent and transparent. Another aspect of the system is that education aimed at a student, in other words, perfects mobility.

In addition, the credit module system combines several types of educational capabilities to provide students with the prospect of continuous learning.

It is no secret that everything has a creative history, with no exception to the credit-module system. Its first roots go back to the US. The credit-module system created in it is considered one of the first to be introduced, and it has contributed to the development of a credit-module system in higher education institutions of the world, including European countries.

So what led to the establishment of a credit-module system in America? At the same time, of course, the subjects that still lost their reflection in practice at those times, including Latin, which by that time had already become a dead language, were translated as a separate language. As a result, universities became a place where high school representatives studied for authority, not a division that prepared standards which benefited the state. This changed by 1869, after Charles Elliott, then a leading thinker, was elected president of Harvard University.

It canceled strictly defined curriculums at the university, allowing students to choose and study the subjects they wanted, interested in, among the subjects offered in the curriculum. As a result, Harvard University was revived. The reason for this is that in order to interest the student, teachers also needed to conduct unusual and effective transitions and research on themselves to interest the student. In this way, subjects with low levels of importance for that period were removed from the curriculum. However, having abandoned strict curriculums, the university raised questions about the order in which the student's criteria for moving from course to course and graduation should be arranged and how much knowledge a student needs to acquire in order to be formed as a specialist. In those days, Harvard University found the following solution to this question: symbolic units of measurement (loans) were distributed to each subject based on its curriculum load. And it is stipulated that the student must collect a certain amount of loans. This will begin to determine the development of curricula and fitness for a particular level of education based on the number of loans it has accumulated.

European countries also developed a new ECTS (European Credit Transfer System) in 1989, based on the American credit system and the Niderladian higher education system. As a result of the introduction of the rules of this credit-module system, student exchange began to develop between universities in European countries.

By 1999, an international forum developing cooperation between the ministries of higher education in European countries, known as the Bologna process, began operating in Europe. According to him, the three-point "bachelor-master-doctor" structure of training specialists in order to improve and improve the quality of education and to ensure transparency will be implemented in two phases throughout a single credit education system: higher education (bachelor's degree) and postgraduate education (doctor).

So what are the advantages of U.S. Higher Education if it switches to this system.

First of all, this system guarantees that the academic knowledge acquired by the student at the university where he or she is studying will be recognized in higher education institutions in a number of countries. And again, members of this system, or students, will be able to restore, move, and complete their studies to another study place.

Today, because of the ECTS system, the amount of loans that students must accumulate in a year is 60. If we consider this to be two semesters, it will be necessary to collect 30 credits per semester. If the bachelor's program is 3-4 years old, it is obligatory for a student to collect between 180 and 240 loans to win a bachelor's degree and 60 to 120 loans to complete a 1-2 year master's program

The principles of the credit-module system are to organize student-oriented education, achieve transparency in education, strengthen flexibility in education, and strengthen student mobility. In other words, this system is not only the process of organizing education but also a model of evaluation based on a collection of modular teaching technologies and a credit measure. Although conducting it as a whole is a

serene and complex systematic process, the use of this system in higher education is also a beneficial way for both a student and, of course, a higher education institution.

Bibliography

1. Abbasova, N. K. (2020). O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA OLMOSHLARNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI. In *МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 472-476).
2. Mirzayeva, D. (2020). OCCURRENCE OF PRAGMALINGUISTIC FEATURES OF PAREMIAS. In *ФИЛОСОФИЯ ИННОВАЦИЙ И СОЦИОЛОГИЯ БУДУЩЕГО В ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ КУЛЬТУРЫ: НАУЧНЫЙ ДИАЛОГ* (pp. 233-235).
3. Shodiyeva, G., & Ismatova, S. (2022). O'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO'Z TURKUMLARI MASALASI. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(7), 103-105.
4. Shodiyeva, G. N. K., & Dustmatov, H. (2022). CLASSIFICATION OF WORDS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH: IN THE EXAMPLE OF VERBS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 234-237.
5. Sotvoldiyevna, U. D. (2022). Political Euphemisms in English and Uzbek Languages (A Comparative Analysis). *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 9, 92-96.
6. Usmonova, D. (2022). PRINCIPLES OF DIVISION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(2), 60-65.
7. Ганиев, Б. С., & Ганиева, М. С. (2020). Семья как важный социальный фактор формирования предпринимательских навыков у молодежи (Опыт Узбекистана). In *Проблемы социальной психологии и социальной работы* (pp. 25-27).
8. ГАНИЕВ, Б., & Ганиева, М. С. (2019). Религиозно-исламские и духовные корни предпринимательской деятельности в Средней Азии. In *ИДЕАЛЫ И ЦЕННОСТИ ИСЛАМА В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ XXI ВЕКА* (pp. 332-335).
9. Maxmudova, N. (2021). BIRD NAMES REALLY MATTER: FEATURES OF ORNITHONYMES IN LANGUAGE. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 116-118.
10. Maxmudova, N. (2021). LEXICAL-SEMANTIC GROUP OF ORNITHONYMS IN LANGUAGE AND THEIR USE. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2021(5), 107-116.
11. Фазилдинова, С. Н. (2016). Technique of correcting mistakes of spoken language in the classroom. *Молодой ученый*, (7-2), 111-113.

12. Abduolimova, M. N., & Fazildinova, S. N. (2020). SINTAKSIS-UNIVERSAL TIL QATLAMI SIFATIDA O'ZBEK TILI GRAMMATIKASIDA TASNIFLANISHI. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION*, 1(5), 323-326.